

PHILOSOPHY

THE PROBLEM OF MAN IN PHILOSOPHY

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Abstract

Man as the main driving force of society is in the focus of attention of many disciplines, philosophy is no exception. The philosophical doctrine of man is called anthropology. She studies the nature, essence, meaning and value of human life, as well as the features and characteristics of human existence. The difference between the philosophical doctrine of man and other sciences is that it explores the most common problems of human existence, the specifics of human existence as a species. Such problems are the problems of anthroposociogenesis – the origin of man and human society, the meaning of human existence as a species and the meaning of life of an individual, freedom and the need for human actions, etc. At the turn of the XX-XXI centuries, the problem of man becomes the central philosophical knowledge. There is an increased attention to what is called in philosophy "existential problematics" to questions about the meaning of life and the value of human existence.

Keywords: personality, moral values, freedom, choice, will.

Introduction: Philosophy studies a person as a person from various aspects. This is evident from the works of world philosophers such as: "Thought and Life" — Sigmund Freud, "Being and Time" — Martin Heidegger, "A Treatise on Man. On easy nature, on human virtues" — Thomas Hobbes, "Biophilosophy" - Erasim Copernicus, "On Mind and Soul: Psychological knowledge and actions" — Aristotle, "The concept of personality" - Carl Rogers, "Good and Bad"— Friedrich Nietzsche, "Problems of the Soul" - Socrates, "Zoopolis. Animals and Politics" - Donna Haravi, "For narpouchou" - Arthur Schopenhauer, etc

The results of the study. One of the key issues is the problem of free will and certainty. The problem of free will and certainty is one of the most controversial topics in philosophy. There are many philosophers who have researched and discussed this problem, each offering their own theories and hypotheses.

One of the most famous philosophers dealing with this problem is Aristotle. He believed that all phenomena in the world occur for certain reasons and laws, and that man, as a part of this world, also obeys these laws. According to his views, there is no free will, since a person's actions are determined by his character, upbringing, education and external circumstances.

On the other hand, some philosophers, such as David Hume and Jean-Paul Sartre, argue that free will exists. Although they have different points of view on the causes and mechanisms of free will, both believe that a person has the ability to choose and make decisions, regardless of external factors. For Hume, free will is the feeling of freedom that we experience when choosing between two alternatives, even if our decisions are still determined by our attitudes and desires. Sartre believed that free will stems from an awareness of our essential freedom and responsibility for our actions.

There are other theories and hypotheses. For example, in compatibilism, the idea of compatibility of free will and certainty is put forward. According to this theory, free will and certainty can exist simultaneously

if you look at them from different levels of analysis. A prominent representative of compatibilism is Thomas Hobbs, who argued that we have free will in the sense that we can act according to our desires and motives, regardless of predestination. It is important to note that this problem is linked to many other issues, such as the relationship between freedom and morality, the role of chance in determining our actions, etc. There are many hypotheses and theories in philosophy, and each of them has its own supporters and opponents. The problem of free will and certainty remains an actively discussed and researched topic.

There is also the problem of self-awareness and awareness of one's place and role in the world. Philosophy is interested in questions about the meaning of life, satisfaction, happiness and the achievements of a full and meaningful existence. The problem of self-awareness and awareness of one's place and role in the world is one of the fundamental themes in philosophy. This problem concerns a person's ability to recognize himself as an individual and understand his place in the world around him.

One of the first philosophers to consider this topic was Descartes. In his philosophical work "Reflections on the First Philosophy", he hypothesized that awareness of one's existence can be represented as the thought "I think, therefore I exist" (Cogito, ergo sum). Descartes identified awareness of his existence with self-awareness, believing that it was the thought of his own existence that was the basis for all other thoughts and cognition in general.

The emergence of the problem of self-awareness and awareness of one's place and role in the world is also associated with the development of philosophy of consciousness and phenomenology in the 20th century. Phenomenology, based on the works of Edmund Husserl and Martin Heidegger, explores the essence of awareness and understanding of the world through direct perception and reflection. She notes that awareness of one's place and role in the world is an integral part of every person's life experience.

There are various hypotheses about the nature of self-awareness and awareness of one's place and role in the world. Some philosophers, such as Rene Descartes and Emanuel Kant, believe that awareness of one's place and role in the world is an innate mental act that is inherent in every intelligent being.

Other theories, such as Nietzsche's philosophy and the essential approach of Martin Heidegger's philosophy, argue that self-awareness and awareness of one's place and role in the world is a process of exploration and self-reflection. They believe that our place and role in the world are shaped through the actions and choices we make, and that self-awareness as autonomous individuals requires constant self-critical reflection.

There are also various religious and metaphysical interpretations of the problem of self-awareness and awareness of one's place and role in the world. For example, in some forms of Judaism and Christianity, the problem of self-awareness is considered as a relationship between an individual and higher forces such as God, ideals, fate and destiny. Other issues, common human problems, moral and ethical problems. What principles and values should we be guided by in our actions and limitations? What is morality and what moral qualities should we fulfill? Common human problems include a wide range of aspects of one's life, from physical and psychological well-being to social and moral dilemmas. In philosophy, moral and ethical issues are especially significant because they try to understand and make sense of our actions, norms of behavior and principles that guide us in the world.

Conclusions: One of the most basic problems of philosophy is understanding the nature of morality and ethics. Questions include: are there objective moral principles, or are they all relative and depend on the cultural context? What is the basis of moral law or error? What standards of behavior should we follow and why?

The second important issue is free will and responsibility. There has been a long-standing debate among philosophers about whether we are free to act or whether everyone is subject to determinism (the idea that our actions are predetermined by external factors). This affects the question of our personal responsibility and the possibility of punishment for our actions.

The third problem concerns public order and justice. What principles should we apply to create a fair society? What rules of conduct and resource allocation are morally and ethically justified? How can we achieve a balance between individual freedom and concern for the collective good?

Philosophers have been researching these problems for many centuries. In ancient Greece, philosophers such as Socrates, Plato and Aristotle explored issues of morality and ethics. Later philosophers such as Immanuel Kant and John Stuart Mill developed various ethical theories and foundations of moral choice.

There are several hypotheses and theories about solving these problems. For example, there are hypotheses that moral norms are universal and unchangeable, while others consider them to be the result of cultural or social conditions. In the theory of moral justice, there is a division between the socialist and the liberal point of view. The former believe that justice includes an even distribution of resources and the protection of all their rights. The latter defend the idea of free markets and the will of people to distribute the benefits of society.

However, these questions and debates in philosophy continue to this day, contributing to our understanding of the world and our morality.

Scientists and philosophers tirelessly explore these and other issues in order to understand and explain the nature and problems of human existence. Finding answers to these questions helps to better understand and find meaning in our lives and our place in the world.

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